

Healing Efficiency Unveiled : Comparing Cyanoacrylate and Sutures In Third Molar Extractions

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Abstract

Objective - This prospective clinical study compared the clinical outcomes of N-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate tissue adhesive and 3-0 silk sutures for wound closure following mandibular third molar surgeries. **Material and Methods:** Ten patients aged 18–35 years with symmetrical impacted mandibular third molars were randomly divided into two groups: Group A (tissue adhesive) and Group B (Silk Sutures). Clinical parameters, including pain, bleeding, swelling, and wound healing, were assessed postoperatively on Day 1 and Day 7 using visual analog scales and standardized criteria. Statistical analysis was conducted using independent t-tests and chi-square tests. **Results:** On Day 1, the adhesive group demonstrated significantly lower pain and bleeding scores compared to the suture group, indicating superior immediate outcomes. Wound healing was also significantly better in the adhesive group, with 100% of cases showing good healing, in contrast to 40% in the suture group. By Day 7, swelling reduction was significantly greater in the adhesive group, reflecting faster recovery and improved patient comfort. Long-term healing outcomes were comparable between the two groups. N-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate tissue adhesive provided several advantages, including reduced operating time, easier application, and improved postoperative comfort due to its bacteriostatic properties, superior hemostasis, and reduced swelling. Additionally, the adhesive eliminated the risk of needle prick injuries, contributing to greater patient satisfaction and better cosmetic results. **Conclusions :** These findings suggest that N-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate tissue adhesive is a reliable and efficient alternative to silk sutures for wound closure in mandibular third molar surgeries, offering benefits for both clinical outcomes and patient recovery.

Introduction

Wound closure in any surgical procedure aims to promote primary healing. The goal of wound closure should be to achieve precise wound approximation, decrease the risk to the patient, easy handling and working properties of the wound closure material, and most importantly is low infection rate.¹ Mandibular third molar removal is a routine procedure performed in the dental office. Most surgeons agree that surgical time, trauma, and difficulty level of the impacted 3rd molar are important factors in assessing post operative pain, swelling, bleeding, and trismus. After the removal of the impacted mandibular third molars, the conventional method is to suture the surgical wound.²

A variety of suture materials are commercially available that may be divided into absorbable and non-absorbable and categorized as monofilament and multi-filament variants. There are different forms of intraoral suture materials including nylon, silk, cotton, polyglycapron, polylactic acid, and polyglycolic acid. Certain materials can interfere

with optimal wound healing and cause excessive scar formation. The optimal suture should have high tensile strength, knot security, and be easy to handle.³

Absorbable suture material, e.g., polyglactin 910 (Vicryl) has been used in many operative procedures. Vicryl is considered a safe, non-toxic, non-immunogenic product. Polyglactin 910 is available both uncoated and coated; triclosan is typically used for coating (Vicryl plus)⁴. Suturing in this area is not always easy, due to in accessible areas, time consumption, and the requirement of good suturing skills². It is also known that suture material increases the risk of wound sepsis by serving as an adhesive foreign body⁵. To overcome these disadvantages, an alternative to the suture tissue adhesive such as cyanoacrylate bio-adhesive has come into use.²

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Cyanoacrylate glue is the general term for the quick bonding super glues used as two separate liquids, one for pouring into the mold and another used sparingly as a hardener in the case of cyanoacrylate glue, the hardener is water. cyanoacrylate glue is placed on a dry surface the glue does not bond with the surface. But with the slightest amount of water, which could include the moisture in the air, the glue's molecules react and form a tight chain between the bonded surfaces. cyanoacrylate glue generates its heat for faster curing. This heat may damage the soft tissue and hamper its blood supply. To avoid this; manufacturers have incorporated long chains of a methyl group due to which the polymerization process is elongated and the rate of heat generation is prolonged. Polymerization of the material occurs within 10–15 seconds.⁶

Surgical glues should have some essential requirements, such as adequate adhesive strength, polymerization also in a moist environment, bio-compatibility, and gradual resorption without foreign body response.⁷

N- butyl Cyanoacrylate is used as a surgical dressing on extraction wounds, fixation of mandibular fractures, healing of intra-oral wounds, fixation of free gingival grafts & healing of periodontal flaps⁸. They are recommended for their hemostatic and anti-inflammatory features and high adhesion ability in a moist environment⁹.

Cyanoacrylate has theoretical advantages over conventional suture closure in that no dressing needs to be applied over the incision, it is immediately water proof, no suture has to be removed and patients are often more satisfied with the cosmetic result¹⁰.

Material and Methods

The Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre in Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India, undertook a prospective randomized trial.

Sample Size

A study was conducted involving ten patients aged 18 to 35 years, without any gender restrictions. The selection criteria were based on preoperative OPG indicating the presence of impacted mandibular third molars. The participants were then categorized into two groups, namely Group A (n-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate) and Group B (3-0 silk sutures,) each consisting of 5 Individuals.

Group A :- "The closure was performed using n-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate adhesive after the surgical removal of the impacted third molar."

Group B :- The closure was performed using 3-0 silk sutures after the surgical removal of the impacted third molar.

Inclusion Criteria

- Impacted Mandibular Third Molars
- Age of patient –18 - 35 yrs of Age
- Class I and class II impacted mandibular third molars (Pell & Gregory Classification)
- Position A and Position B impacted mandibular third molars (Pell & Gregory Classification)
- Patient who was willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Age of Patient – Above 35 years of age

- Class III impacted mandibular third molars (Pell & Gregory Classification)
- Position C impacted mandibular third molars (Pell & Gregory Classification)
- Medically Compromised Patient
- Compromised Bone Health
- Pregnant Females

- Any bony pathology related to impacted mandibular third molar
- Patient's Allergic to any component of the Material used.
- Not willing to participate in the course of Study.

This study was conducted from November 1, 2023 to June 10, 2024).

The study was conducted at the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre in Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India, undertook a prospective randomized trial.

All participants have read and signed informed consent form.

The study protocol was approved by the by the Ethical Committee of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre in Ghaziabad.

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Group A

Figure -1 (Pre-operative OPG)

Figure - Adhesive Placed

Group B

Figure - 15 (Pre-operative OPG)

Figure - Suture Placed

Result
Gender Distribution of Study Subjects

Intergroup Comparison of Mean Change In Pain Scores at Different Time Intervals

	Pre Op		1st Post Op Day		Change at 1st Post op Day		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Suture Group	6.20	1.303	6.60	1.516	-0.40	1.816	0.011 (Sig)
Adhesive Group	5.20	1.483	4.20	0.836	1.00	1.732	
	Pre Op		7th Post Op Day		Change at 7th Post op Day		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Suture Group	6.20	1.303	1.00	1.000	5.20	1.788	0.749 (Non-Sig)
Adhesive Group	5.20	1.483	0.40	0.547	4.80	1.923	

Intergroup Comparison of Bleeding Scores at Different Time Intervals

1st Post Op			
	Mean	SD	P value
Suture Group	1.60	1.140	0.001 (Sig)
Adhesive Group	0.60	0.894	
7 th Post Op			
	Mean	SD	P value
Suture Group	0.00	0.000	1.000 (Non-Sig)
Adhesive Group	0.00	0.000	

Intergroup Comparison of Healing Scores between the Suture and Adhesive Group at 1st and 7th Post Operative Day

		Very Poor	Poor	Good	P value
1st Post Op day	Suture Group	1 20.0%	2 40.0%	2 40.0%	0.012 (Sig)
	Adhesive Group	0 .0%	0 .0%	5 100.0%	
		Good	Very Good	Excellent	P value
7 th Post op Day	Suture Group	2 40.0%	2 40.0%	1 20.0%	0.282 (Non-Sig)
	Adhesive Group	0 .0%	3 60.0%	2 40.0%	

Intergroup Comparison of Change In Swelling Scores at 1st and 7th Post Op Day – EG

Intergroup Comparison of Change In Swelling Scores at 1st and 7th Post Op Day –TM

Intergroup Comparison of Change In Swelling Scores at 1st and 7th Post Op Day –TP

Discussion

Wound healing is a complex, multi-phase process that can be influenced by various factors. This study focused on evaluating the effectiveness of N-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate (a tissue adhesive) compared to 3-0 silk sutures in intraoral wound closure following mandibular third molar surgery. The findings highlight several important insights and improvements that come from using cyanoacrylate in place of sutures.

One of the key findings is the significantly reduced wound closure time when using cyanoacrylate, in line with previous studies (Gogulanathan et al., 2015), which reported a decrease in operating time when using fibrin sealant compared to suturing. This can translate into a reduction in overall surgical duration, potentially minimizing complications associated with longer procedures (Lars Anderson et al., 2010). Additionally, cyanoacrylate provided quicker hemostasis, with significantly lower bleeding scores on the first postoperative day, confirming its superior hemostatic properties as reported in other studies (Al-Belasy and Amer, 2012).

Regarding postoperative pain and swelling, this study found that the adhesive group experienced significantly lower pain scores at Day 1, though this difference was not as marked by Day 7. Swelling was also significantly reduced by Day 7 in the adhesive group, suggesting that the tissue adhesive may help to minimize inflammatory responses compared to sutures. This finding aligns with Mahat et al. (2010), who reported less swelling in the sutureless group. However, the postoperative bleeding was notably lower in the adhesive group, further supporting the hemostatic advantage of cyanoacrylate (Ghoreshian et al., 2012).

The healing rates, although better in the adhesive group on Day 1, showed no statistically significant difference between the groups by Day 7, suggesting that both techniques ultimately allow for comparable long-term healing. The results regarding wound dehiscence and infection showed no significant difference, indicating that both methods are similarly effective in preventing wound complications over time. However, the bacteriostatic properties of cyanoacrylate offer an additional advantage in reducing the risk of infection, as suggested by Giray et al. (1997).

While cyanoacrylate demonstrated notable advantages in terms of wound closure time, pain relief, bleeding control, and swelling reduction, it did not show a statistically significant difference in long-term healing or the occurrence of wound infections. This could be due to the natural course of healing and the relatively short follow-up period in this study.

Conclusion

In conclusion, N-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate tissue adhesive provides a highly effective, efficient, and patient friendly alternative to silk sutures for intraoral wound closure. It offers significant advantages, particularly in reducing surgical time, improving hemostasis, and enhancing postoperative comfort. Given the results, tissue adhesive can be considered a preferable option in mandibular third molar surgeries, though further studies with longer follow-up periods are needed to confirm its long-term outcomes and safety.

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